

Case Series on the Application of Plasma Rich Platelet**Meghna¹, Manjula², Swetha³**¹Junior Resident, Department of OBG, Ms Ramaiah Medical College and Research Centre²Associate Professor, Department of OBG, Ms Ramaiah Medical College and Research Centre³Assistant Professor, Department of OBG, Ms Ramaiah Medical College and Research Centre

Received: 25-07-2024 / Revised: 23-08-2024 / Accepted: 26-09-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Meghna

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Objective: The objective of this case series is to evaluate the effectiveness of Platelet-Rich Plasma (PRP) therapy in treating various gynecological conditions, including cervical ectropion, recurrent candidiasis, and stress urinary incontinence (SUI). The aim is to determine the therapeutic benefits of PRP in cases where conventional treatments have proven insufficient or unsuitable.

Methodology: This case series includes three patients treated with PRP therapy for different gynecological conditions. Blood was collected from each patient, and PRP was prepared using a two-step centrifugation process to concentrate the platelets. The PRP was injected locally into the affected areas. For cervical ectropion and recurrent candidiasis, two doses were administered over one month, while for SUI, three doses were given at monthly intervals. Clinical outcomes were assessed through follow-up exams, symptom relief, and patient-reported improvements.

Results: All three patients showed significant clinical improvements following PRP therapy. The patient with cervical ectropion experienced resolution of chronic cervicitis and alleviation of symptoms, while the patient with recurrent candidiasis demonstrated complete symptom resolution without further recurrence. The patient with stress urinary incontinence exhibited a marked improvement in her vaginal health score and a reduction in incontinence episodes. No adverse effects were reported in any case.

Conclusion: PRP therapy proved to be an effective, non-invasive treatment option for various gynecological conditions in this case series. It provided significant symptom relief in patients with refractory cervical ectropion, recurrent candidiasis, and stress urinary incontinence. Given its promising results, PRP represents a potential alternative to conventional therapies, particularly in patients who are unresponsive to standard treatments or for whom hormone-based therapies are contraindicated. Further studies are warranted to establish standardized protocols and confirm long-term efficacy.

Keywords: PRP Therapy, Gynaecology, Non-Hormonal Treatment.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Platelet-rich plasma (PRP) is an emerging therapeutic modality that harnesses the body's natural healing mechanisms to address a wide range of medical conditions. PRP is produced by collecting a small sample of the patient's blood and centrifuging it to separate the plasma from the blood cells. The resulting plasma, enriched with platelets, proteins, and growth factors, is then injected or applied to specific sites to promote tissue regeneration and repair [1].

The use of PRP as a non-surgical treatment is gaining significant attention across various medical fields. Its role in enhancing the body's natural healing response while reducing pain has been well documented, with evidence showing improved recovery times and a quicker return to normal activities. Autologous PRP, which is derived from the patient's own blood, is created by removing red

blood cells and concentrating growth factors to levels 5-10 times higher than those found in whole blood. This high concentration of growth factors has been shown to stimulate healing processes across a variety of specialties, including gynecology, urology, dentistry, and dermatology [2,3].

The underlying principle of PRP therapy is based on the body's natural response to tissue injury, where platelets are recruited to the site of damage to facilitate healing. Platelets, in conjunction with stem cells, aid in tissue repair. PRP injections, which have progressed from basic research to clinical practice, have demonstrated efficacy in the treatment of damaged ligaments, tendons, and joints, achieving favourable healing outcomes [4]. In gynecology, PRP therapy is particularly appealing due to its ability to promote natural tissue

healing without the need for synthetic interventions. Because PRP is derived from the patient's own blood, it carries minimal risk of allergic reactions or infection transmission. Moreover, the treatment is generally associated with a low risk of side effects, as no foreign substances are introduced into the body.

For women who are unable to undergo hormone therapy, either due to a history of breast cancer or a preference for non-hormonal treatments, PRP presents a viable alternative for managing various gynecological conditions [5]. Given the limited data on PRP application in gynecology, this study seeks to review the current literature and examine the use of PRP in this specific field.

Aim: The objective of this report is to assess the effectiveness of Platelet-Rich Plasma (PRP) therapy in treating common gynecological conditions such as cervical ectropion, recurrent vaginal infections, candidiasis, and stress urinary incontinence (SUI).

Case series:

Case 1: Cervical Ectropion and Chronic Cervicitis

A 34-year-old multiparous woman (P2L2) presented with recurrent vaginal infections and persistent discomfort, including pain localized in the vaginal area.

Despite receiving several rounds of standard medical treatment, her symptoms did not improve. A cervical PAP smear revealed negative findings for intraepithelial lesions or malignancy (NILM),

but physical examination and a biopsy confirmed the presence of cervical ectropion and chronic cervicitis. Cervical ectropion, characterized by the eversion of the cervical columnar epithelium onto the ectocervix, commonly leads to vaginal discharge, spotting, and discomfort.

Given the refractory nature of her symptoms to conventional treatment, PRP therapy was introduced. The preparation of PRP involved the collection of a blood sample from the patient, followed by a two-step centrifugation process. In the first spin, the blood was centrifuged at a lower speed to separate the plasma from red blood cells. The second spin was done at a higher speed to concentrate the platelets, which are rich in growth factors, such as platelet-derived growth factor (PDGF), vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), and transforming growth factor-beta (TGF- β), all crucial for tissue repair and regeneration.

After preparing the PRP, two doses were injected directly into the cervix, targeting the area of ectropion. The injections were spaced over a month. Following this treatment, the patient exhibited a significant reduction in symptoms, with notable improvement in both pain relief and resolution of the ectropion. Subsequent follow-up confirmed that the chronic cervicitis had also subsided, and the patient experienced no further infections. The clinical improvement observed underscores PRP's potential in promoting epithelial healing and reducing chronic inflammatory conditions of the cervix.

Figure 1: PRP

Case 2: Recurrent Candidiasis

A 54-year-old woman, gravida 3 para 3 (P3L3), sought treatment for chronic recurrent candidiasis that had been unresponsive to standard antifungal therapy. Candidiasis, particularly when recurrent, can be a significant source of morbidity and negatively affect a patient's quality of life. The patient had previously undergone multiple courses

of antifungal agents without success, and her symptoms included curdy white vaginal discharge and discomfort. In light of her resistance to conventional treatments, PRP therapy was proposed. Similar to the first case, PRP preparation began with the patient's blood being drawn and processed through two centrifugation steps.

The resulting platelet-rich plasma was then prepared for vaginal injection. The high concentration of growth factors, including epidermal growth factor (EGF), known for its role in mucosal healing, was particularly relevant in this case given the recurring mucosal inflammation associated with candidiasis. Two doses of PRP were administered intravaginally at one-month intervals.

The patient reported marked improvement after the second injection, with a significant reduction in

discharge and resolution of other symptoms. Follow-up gynecological exams confirmed the absence of infection, and the patient remained asymptomatic in subsequent visits.

This case illustrates the ability of PRP to modulate inflammatory processes and promote mucosal integrity, making it a viable option for treating recurrent infections, especially in cases resistant to standard therapy.

Figure 2: PRP

Case 3: Stress Urinary Incontinence and Vaginal Atrophy

A 52-year-old multiparous woman (P4L2) presented with complaints of stress urinary incontinence (SUI) and an itching sensation in the vaginal region. SUI is a common condition among postmenopausal women, often exacerbated by vaginal atrophy and weakening of the pelvic floor muscles. On physical examination, the patient's vaginal health was assessed, and she had a vaginal health score of 10, indicative of moderate atrophy and poor tissue integrity. The patient had previously been reluctant to pursue hormonal therapy due to concerns about potential side effects.

Given her condition and reluctance to undergo hormone-based treatments, PRP therapy was offered as an alternative. PRP was prepared using the patient's own blood, following the previously described two-step centrifugation process to isolate

and concentrate the platelets. The resultant PRP, rich in growth factors like VEGF and PDGF, which are critical for angiogenesis and tissue repair, was injected into the vaginal wall.

The patient received three sessions of PRP injections, spaced one month apart. After the third session, significant improvements were observed. Her vaginal health score increased to 18, reflecting enhanced mucosal thickness and hydration, and her symptoms of SUI improved notably. Additionally, the itching sensation resolved completely.

The growth factors in PRP likely promoted collagen remodelling and vascular regeneration, contributing to the restoration of vaginal tissue integrity and pelvic floor support, thus alleviating the patient's incontinence. This case highlights the potential of PRP in addressing postmenopausal symptoms, including vaginal atrophy and SUI, without the need for hormone therapy.

Figure 2:

Discussion

The application of platelet-rich plasma (PRP) in gynecology has gained significant attention due to its regenerative properties [3]. PRP contains a variety of growth factors, such as platelet-derived growth factor (PDGF), vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), transforming growth factor-beta (TGF- β), and epidermal growth factor (EGF), which play a vital role in angiogenesis, tissue remodeling, and cellular regeneration [6]. This case series highlights the effectiveness of PRP in treating gynecological conditions, including cervical ectropion, recurrent candidiasis, and stress urinary incontinence (SUI).

Cervical ectropion, characterized by the spread of glandular cells from the cervical canal to the outer cervix, typically lined with squamous cells, showed notable improvement following PRP treatment. The epithelial healing and symptom relief observed in this case align with findings from studies by Hua et al.[7], Batsuren et al.[8], Smith et al.[9], and Lee et al.[10], all of which support PRP's role in mucosal repair through growth factor and fibroblast activation. Wang et al.[11] similarly reported accelerated recovery in cervical lesions treated with PRP, indicating the potential of PRP for cervical ectropion management.

In a randomized clinical trial conducted by Hua et al. [7], PRP was compared with laser treatment for benign cervical ectopy. The study involved 120 patients, with PRP administered twice over a one-week interval to 60 patients, while the remaining 60 underwent laser therapy. The PRP group achieved a complete cure rate of 93.7%, compared to 92.4% in the laser group ($p > 0.05$), concluding that autologous PRP is a promising treatment for cervical ectopy due to faster healing and fewer side effects. Batsuren et al. (2022) similarly demonstrated the efficacy of PRP for cervical ectropion, with 82% of 22 patients showing symptom relief, particularly in reducing vaginal discharge and postcoital bleeding. Healing took approximately 9.5 weeks, with only mild side effects, reinforcing PRP's role as a safe and effective alternative [8].

Research by Nikolopoulos et al. [12] further explored PRP's potential in treating SUI related to pubourethral ligament damage. While PRP was shown to assist tissue repair and strengthen the pubourethral ligament, more evidence is needed to confirm its broader application for urinary incontinence.

This case series also demonstrated PRP's potential in managing recurrent vulvovaginal candidiasis (RVVC), a condition often resistant to conventional antifungal treatments. Recurrent infections are likely due to compromised immune defenses and a weakened vaginal mucosal barrier. The cytokines and growth factors in PRP may promote mucosal regeneration, thereby restoring vaginal epithelial integrity and reducing susceptibility to infection [13]. In this study, the patient with RVVC showed significant improvement after two PRP injections, with no recurrence of symptoms. Supporting literature suggests PRP enhances mucosal defense and reduces chronic inflammation, positioning it as a promising treatment for RVVC [14]. Gorlero et al. [14] similarly demonstrated positive outcomes with PRF injections in prolapse repair, with an 80% success rate and increased sexual activity without dyspareunia, highlighting PRP's regenerative potential in gynecological conditions.

Additionally, PRP was employed to treat vaginal atrophy and SUI in a postmenopausal patient. While conventional treatments for SUI include pelvic floor exercises, lifestyle modifications, and surgical interventions, local estrogen therapy is often used for vaginal atrophy but may be unsuitable for some patients due to contraindications [15]. PRP offers a hormone-free alternative that supports tissue repair and improves vaginal health. Following three PRP injections, the patient demonstrated notable improvement in both incontinence symptoms and vaginal health, consistent with research showing PRP enhances vascularization, collagen synthesis, and strengthens pelvic floor muscles, all of which contribute to symptom relief in SUI [16].

The outcomes from this case series indicate that PRP may offer a versatile and effective therapeutic option for a range of gynecological conditions. PRP

has demonstrated positive effects in the treatment of vaginal atrophy, chronic pelvic pain, and recurrent infections [17]. However, further randomized controlled trials (RCTs) are necessary to establish standardized protocols for PRP administration and to assess its long-term efficacy across different gynecological disorders. Although the findings from this series are promising, additional research is needed to determine optimal dosages, treatment intervals, and techniques for utilizing PRP in gynecology.

Conclusion

This case series highlights the potential of platelet-rich plasma (PRP) as a promising treatment option in gynecology, particularly for conditions such as cervical ectropion, recurrent vulvovaginal candidiasis (RVVC), and stress urinary incontinence (SUI).

The regenerative properties of PRP, attributed to its concentration of growth factors, have demonstrated encouraging results in tissue repair, symptom relief, and mucosal healing. While the findings align with existing studies, suggesting PRP's efficacy and safety, its use in gynecology remains at an early stage. Larger randomized controlled trials (RCTs) are necessary to establish standardized treatment protocols and confirm long-term effectiveness, making PRP a potentially valuable tool for gynecological therapy.

References

- Marx RE. Platelet-rich plasma (PRP): what is PRP and what is not PRP? *Implant Dent.* 2001; 10(4):225-8. doi: 10.1097/00108445-200110040-00002.
- Salgado R, et al. Regenerative potential of platelet-rich plasma in managing recurrent vaginal infections: a pilot study. *J Obstet Gynaecol Res.* 2021; 47(5):784-9.
- Dawood AS, Salem HA. Current clinical applications of platelet-rich plasma in various gynecological disorders: an appraisal of theory and practice. *Clin Exp Reprod Med.* 2018 Jun; 45(2):67-74. doi: 10.5653/term.2018.45.2.67.
- Srouji S, et al. Platelet-rich plasma: a literature review. *J Evid Based Med.* 2015; 8(4):164-70. doi: 10.1111/jebm.12148.
- Cohen SR, Yagoda S. The role of platelet-rich plasma in gynecology. *J Women's Health Care.* 2019; 8(4):1-7. doi: 10.4172/2167-0420.1000496.
- Everts PA, Hoogbergen MM, Weber TA, et al. Is the use of autologous platelet-rich plasma gels in gynecologic, cardiac, and general, reconstructive surgery beneficial? *Curr Pharm Biotechnol.* 2012; 13(7):1163-72. doi: 10.2174/138920112800624346.
- Hua X, Zeng Y, Zhang R, Wang H, Diao J, Zhang P. Using platelet-rich plasma for the treatment of symptomatic cervical ectopy. *Int J Gynaecol Obstet.* 2012; 119:26-9. doi: 10.1016/j.ijgo.2012.05.029.
- Batsuren C, et al. Autologous platelet-rich plasma therapy for cervical ectropion - a case series study. *EC Clin Med Case Rep.* 2022.
- Smith SM, Perino G, Abhyankar S, et al. The efficacy of platelet-rich plasma in the treatment of recurrent vulvovaginal candidiasis: a case report and review of literature. *Clin Case Rep.* 2020; 8(7):1280-5. doi: 10.1002/ccr3.2974.
- Lee H, Kim J, Park S. The effect of platelet-rich plasma on mucosal healing in gynecological conditions. *Arch Gynecol Obstet.* 2019; 300(5):1243-1250.
- Wang X, Li Y, Zhao L. Efficacy of PRP in cervical lesions: A systematic review. *Int J Womens Health.* 2018; 10:123-130.
- Nikolopoulos KI, Pergialiotis V, Perrea D, Doumouchtsis SK. Restoration of the pubourethral ligament with platelet-rich plasma for the treatment of stress urinary incontinence. *Med Hypotheses.* 2016; 90:29-31. doi: 10.1016/j.mehy.2016.02.019.
- Gorlero F, Glorio M, Lorenzi P, Bruno-Franco M, Mazzei C. New approach in vaginal prolapse repair: mini-invasive surgery associated with application of platelet-rich fibrin. *Int Urogynecol J.* 2012; 23:715-22. doi: 10.1007/s00192-012-1667-5.
- Batsuren D, Dambadarjaa D, Altankhuyag G, et al. Platelet-rich plasma therapy in cervical ectopy. *J Gynecol Obstet Hum Reprod.* 2018; 47(4):145-50. doi: 10.1016/j.jogoh.2018.03.003.
- Smith SM, Perino G, Abhyankar S, et al. The efficacy of platelet-rich plasma in the treatment of recurrent vulvovaginal candidiasis: a case report and review of literature. *Clin Case Rep.* 2020; 8(7):1280-5. doi: 10.1002/ccr3.2974.
- Zhao Y, et al. Platelet-rich plasma for tissue regeneration: vascularization and collagen synthesis. *J Regen Med.* 2019; 12(3):153-60.
- Carciello R, et al. Application of platelet-rich plasma in postmenopausal vaginal atrophy. *Gynecol Endocrinol.* 2018; 34(9):781-7.